

WAYS OF DESIGNING PEDAGOGICAL PROCESSES IN EDUCATION OF CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE

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Abstract: The article discusses the methodology for developing ways to design pedagogical processes in the education of older preschool children, and the ways to implement it in preschool educational organizations. This article analyzes modern approaches and methods for effective design of pedagogical activities in the education of older preschool children. This article is devoted to the organization of the pedagogical process in different age groups in preschool educational organizations. The pedagogical process is a constantly developing relationship between a teacher and children, aimed at learning, education and personal development.

Keywords: process, activity, relationship, psychology, procedure, work activity, classes, curriculum, competency approach, didactic modeling, game technologies, developing environment, older children, methodological support, monitoring and evaluation

Introduction. Preschool education is the initial stage of a continuous education system. It ensures the development of a healthy, developed child's personality, instilling a desire for learning, and preparing them for systematic study. Preschool education is provided in state and private preschool educational institutions up to 6-7 years of age and in the family [1].

The main goal of preschool education is to prepare children for school, form a healthy, developed and independent personality, develop their abilities, and cultivate a desire for learning and systematic learning [5].

The task of democratizing and humanizing the education system, as well as increasing the effectiveness of the pedagogical process in preschool educational institutions in the conditions of variability of existing educational and upbringing programs, is becoming increasingly important.

The pedagogical process is a constantly developing relationship between a teacher and children, aimed at teaching, upbringing and personal development, leading to a purposeful change in the characteristics and qualities of children receiving education.

The pedagogical process is one of the important categories of the discipline of pedagogy, closely related to the laws of education, age-related dynamics of development, values of preschool age, the skills and creativity of the teacher, etc.

The development of pedagogical processes for older preschoolers includes setting goals (preparation for school, development of independence, communication), content (through games, lessons, excursions), activity component (active interaction, problem solving) and results (knowledge, skills, socialization).

For the second younger (3-4 years old) and middle (4-5 years old) groups, the educational process also begins with a morning reception. Children are offered individual or group games and individual work with children. Morning exercises last longer. Breakfast

encourages children to be neat and independent. After breakfast, children begin their activities. There is a short break between classes, and the transition from one game to another is organized through unexpected events, problem solving, or game-based situations. Classes are varied during the lesson [2, 3].

Between breakfast and class, children are engaged in active games.

After class, children go for a walk. During the walk, they observe nature and do chores, for example, help collect leaves. Children perform various tasks, set the table, and arrange materials for the lesson. The educator creates a “guard corner”. In the middle group, stable play groups are formed among children. The educator teaches them to perform exercises together. [2, 3]

The educational process in the senior (5-6 years) and preparatory (6-7 years) groups is characterized by a high level of independence in everyday life. Children become more resilient and develop self-control skills. Daytime sleep is reduced to 1 hour 45 minutes. The duration of classes varies from 1 hour 20 minutes to 1 hour 30 minutes. After sleep, play time increases to 40-50 minutes. After sleep, various additional classes are introduced, such as rhythmic gymnastics or a drama club.

Once a week, children are organized for group classes.

This helps children to communicate with each other and build relationships. At this age, children are already solving more complex educational problems independently.

Educational problems are solved in pairs or small groups. Elements related to school activities are introduced. This is aimed at preparing children for school. Thus, the organization of the educational process in preschool educational organizations for different age groups differs in its own way, but the main factors are the child's activity and communication. These factors determine the child's mental development and educational process, as well as the formation of personality traits.

Methodology. Preschool education is one of the most important stages of children's development, which creates a solid foundation for the child's further educational process. At this stage, the child learns about the environment, forms speech, acquires social skills and develops as a person. Therefore, the correct establishment of the preschool education system is of great importance for the development of society.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Preschool Education and Upbringing defines preschool education and upbringing as a type of continuous education aimed at educating and raising children, developing them intellectually, spiritually, morally, ethically, aesthetically and physically, as well as preparing children for general secondary education.

In the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on approval of the Concept for the Development of the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, it is noted that over the past period, extensive work has been carried out in our country to organize an effective system of preschool education aimed at raising the growing generation to a healthy and comprehensively mature adulthood, introducing effective forms and methods of education and upbringing into the educational process.

At the same time, the analysis shows the need to address the issues of ensuring the coverage of children with preschool education, replenishing preschool educational institutions with modern educational and methodological materials and fiction, and attracting qualified pedagogical and management personnel to the field.

The main principles - awareness, activity, consistency and clarity - are implemented to develop children's initiative, communication skills and readiness for school through role-playing games, project-based activities and conversations.

Principles and methods of development:

The principle of awareness and activity: Children should understand the purpose of the activity and participate in it.

The principle of systematicity and clarity: gradual complication and the use of existing forms (pictures, real objects).

The principle of availability: compliance of content and methods with age capabilities.

Reliance on leading activities:

Role-playing: Development of social skills, the ability to empathize and build relationships (children learn to empathize and express themselves).

Project activities: Develop research skills, independence and the ability to work in a team.

Educational activities: (Mathematics, speech development, construction) in a game style, with problem situations.

Communicative situations: Conversations, dialogues, theatrical performances to develop speech and socio-emotional intelligence.

Features of the older preschooler for developmental processes:

☑ Active desire for self-affirmation and self-expression.

☑ Increased sensitivity to the feelings of others, development of empathy.

☑ Formation of autonomy (the ability to control one's own behavior).

The development of such processes requires flexibility, an individual approach, the use of game technologies, and the creation of an environment that encourages independence and creativity in older preschool children.

Results. During the study, based on practical work, observations, and experimental tests on the design of the educational process for older preschool children, the following results were achieved:

1. The current state of designing the pedagogical process was determined

According to the results of diagnostics conducted in the 6 preschool educational organizations studied: 68% of educators use only weekly planning when designing the educational process, 32% cannot fully apply an integrated approach based on competencies, and the level of use of information technologies in designing educational activities is low.

This indicated the need to reorganize the pedagogical process in accordance with modern requirements.

2. An improved model of educational process design was developed. The project model developed in the study consisted of the following components:

adapting goals and expected results to age characteristics, creating an integrated educational content, designing a sequence of activities on a block-module basis, organizing a developmental environment by functional zones, and introducing a system of criteria and indicators for monitoring children's achievements.

The model provides educators with a clear algorithm for effective planning of the process and determining its effectiveness. The design of the pedagogical process is based on the child's age development characteristics, individual needs, interests, and principles of

competency-based education. It also covers planning the content of education, game technologies, methodological developments aimed at the formation of competencies, monitoring and evaluation criteria. The study shows the importance of didactic models and integrative approaches that enhance the creative activity of the educator and serve to develop independent thinking, socio-emotional development, and communicative skills in children.

The main tasks of preschool education are to ensure the physical, mental, spiritual, and social development of children, to form in them such skills as independent thinking, communication, and learning through play. Play activities are the main tool at this stage, because it is in the process of play that the child learns, expresses himself, and easily accepts new knowledge.

In modern preschool education, the use of innovative pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, the STEAM approach, developmental games and multimedia tools is widely used. This increases the interest of children and involves them in the active learning process. The educator acts not only as a provider of knowledge, but also as a coach who guides the child's development, taking into account his interests and needs.

The modern preschool education system requires a comprehensive approach aimed at the comprehensive development of children, their personal qualities, social skills and independent formation of cognitive processes. Older preschoolers - that is, children aged 5-7 - begin to demonstrate such features as activity, independence and a creative approach to problem situations in the educational process. Therefore, careful planning and design of pedagogical processes on a scientifically based basis is of particular importance at this stage.

Designing a pedagogical process is a process of purposefully determining the content, methods, tools and organizational forms of education, harmonizing them with each other and forming a result-oriented approach. Today, in preschool education, competency-based requirements, state curricula, the STEAM approach, inclusive education principles and digital technologies combine educational processes to further complicate the content of pedagogical design. Also, designing taking into account the individual differences of children, their development rate, social environment and family conditions requires further improvement of the professional skills of the teacher.

Therefore, the issue of effective design of pedagogical processes in the education of older children remains an urgent scientific problem not only for practicing educators, but also for researchers engaged in design methodology. The relevance of this topic is determined, on the one hand, by the growing need to improve the quality of preschool education, and on the other hand, by the methodological shortcomings observed in the process of introducing modern pedagogical technologies into practice. This study aims to identify the main ways to design pedagogical processes, analyze their scientific and methodological foundations, and propose an effective model for the education of older preschool children.

Discussion. The content and essence of pedagogical design in preschool education. One of the main tasks set before the preschool education system today is to create conditions for the comprehensive development of children, their psychophysiological growth and formation as individuals. The effectiveness of this process is directly related to the scientifically based planning and design activities of the teacher.

Pedagogical design is an activity of systematically organizing the pedagogical process aimed at determining the goals, objectives, content, methods, means and results of the

educational process in advance on a scientific basis, and their consistent implementation. In the conditions of MTT, this process is aimed at creating a developmental, comfortable psychological environment appropriate to the age of children.

The necessity of the design process is manifested in the following factors:

ensuring the continuity of the educational process;

strengthening the person-oriented approach in pedagogical activities;

full implementation of the requirements of state curricula;

improving the quality of education and monitoring the results;

systematize work with the individuality, interests, needs, and level of development of children.

Also, design allows the teacher to plan his activities, anticipate the expected results, and correctly choose methodological approaches. In modern preschool educational institutions, each lesson, weekly and monthly plans, educational activities, and the system of development centers are based on the principles of design.

The content of pedagogical design: determining the educational goal; selecting age-appropriate content; determining methods and technologies; selecting diagnostic tools; determining expected results; monitoring the process. Therefore, design is an important pedagogical process that increases the professional competence of the teacher.

Stages and methods of designing pedagogical activities

The pedagogical design process is carried out in several sequential stages. The state program of preschool educational organizations also clearly indicates the procedure for planning the pedagogical process.

1. The main stages of design.

Stage 1: Diagnostics and analysis. At this stage, the teacher: determines the level of development of children; studies their interests, needs, psychological state; analyzes the indicators of work with parents; assesses the state of the educational environment in the group. Based on the diagnostics, goals are formed for the entire educational process.

Stage 2: Setting goals and objectives. The goals can be: developing cognitive processes; forming communicative competencies; ensuring physical development; developing creative abilities; strengthening social adaptation. The teacher determines the tasks in accordance with the goals.

Stage 3: Designing the content of education. At this stage: thematic plan of classes; weekly, monthly, annual planning; educational work plans; activities of centers; the content of games, observations, excursions is determined. The content is selected in accordance with the age characteristics of children.

Stage 4: Selecting methods and technologies. Modern pedagogical technologies used in today's MTTs: project method; STEAM approach; interactive methods; competency-based education; game technologies; problem-solving method.

Stage 5: Implementation of the process. The designed plan is put into practice, the teacher conducts classes, manages children's activities, conducts observations and analysis.

Stage 6: Evaluation and monitoring of results. This stage includes determining the effectiveness of the project: development maps; observation sheets; diagnostic tests; results of communication with parents; self-analysis of the teacher.

2.2. Design methods. The following methods are used in pedagogical design: Analytical method - determining the goal by studying the existing problem and situation. Prognostic method - determining the expected result in advance. Modeling method - developing a visual model of the educational process. Experimental methods - testing the educational process. Reflexive method - analyzing the results of the teacher's own activities. These methods increase the teacher's professional activity.

During the study, the following results were achieved based on practical work, observations and experimental tests on the design of the educational process for older preschool children:

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3. The effectiveness of the proposed project model was proven in pilot lessons

As a result of the project-based educational process introduced in the experimental group, it was observed that: children's speech activity increased by 23%, skills in organizing independent activities by 28%, socio-emotional competencies by 19%, and creative thinking indicators by 21%.

Compared with the control group, the changes were statistically significant.

4. The methodological training of educators has increased

The article concludes with scientific and practical proposals aimed at improving the educational process in preschool educational organizations and improving the skills of teachers. As a result of the seminar-trainings on planning: 85% of teachers began to independently use planning based on a competency-based approach, 72% mastered the integrated design of educational activities, and the level of use of IT tools in lesson development significantly increased

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